

Greenford | CT 0026.02

Based on 2021 Census Data

CT Highlights

Population
= 1,839

Number of Homes
= 892

Population Density
= 2,968/Km²

5-year Population change = 1.1%

Age Distribution by Gender

53%
Age 55+

29%
Age 25-54

18%
Age 0-24

\$35,280
Average Income
(after-tax)

16.1%
Unemployment
Rate

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Canadian Citizens

Language Spoken at Home

English | 65.6%
Non-official Languages | 13.4%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

■ No certificate, diploma or degree
■ Secondary (high) school diploma or equivalency
■ Postsecondary certificate, diploma or degree

Neighbourhood Homes

\$1,240_(own)
\$1,064_(rent)

Average monthly shelter costs

54%

Rent their home

\$632,000

Average home value

82%

Built before 1980

3%

Major repair needed

31%

Apartment ≥ 5 stories

Public Health
Agency of Canada

Agence de la santé
publique du Canada

Rebecca Ganann | ganann@mcmaster.ca
Caroline Moore | camoore@mcmaster.ca

Institute for
Research on Aging

Aging, Community
and Health
RESEARCH UNIT

LABARGE CENTRE FOR MOBILITY IN AGING

Cite

Siddiqui, S., Orr, E., Ganann, R. On behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team. (2023).

Infographic: Neighbourhood Profile-Greenford.

URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>

Data Source: Statistics Canada. 2021. 5370026.02 [Census tract].

www.statcan.gc.ca